

TEACHING ELEMENTARY STUDENTS TO THINK CREATIVELY

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Annotation: *This article provides the necessary information and resources on teacher responsibilities that should be used to teach creative thinking in primary school students. Based on the information provided in the article, teachers and parents can get the advice they need.*

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The word creativity was first used in 1922 by the American scientist D. Simpson. Through this term, a person described the ability to give up stereotypes, stereotypes, conventional thinking.

Creativity (Lat. Creatio - creation, creation) - this is the ability of man to come up with an unusual idea, the ability to think, to find unique, original solutions to problems, to abandon the traditional forms of thinking. Creativity as a category that develops the individual is an integral part of human thinking, spirituality, not in the multifaceted nature of the knowledge possessed by the individual, but in the process of striving for new ideas, correcting and changing established stereotypes, solving life problems manifests itself in making unexpected and unusual decisions. That is, creativity cannot be achieved by repeating the knowledge given, the main condition in the process of creative thinking is the emergence of a new idea, a new idea. For example, memorizing words in English, even if you "drink water" the rules of grammar, if you don't write an essay, it's all in vain. Imagination therefore plays an important role in the creative thinking process. This is exactly what Albert Einstein meant when he said, "Imagination is more important than knowledge." Often unusual ideas, solutions suddenly come to mind. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to eliminate the homogeneity, the habit in the process of thinking. The content and essence of the concept of creativity is deeply analyzed. However, the scientific-theoretical, scientific-pedagogical aspects of the problem of creativity have not been studied as an object of special scientific research. Primary education in particular is one of the most important types of education in the life of every

child, and at this stage of education, teachers have a great responsibility. In other words, the creative activity of primary school teachers still requires special study. E.Yu.Artem`eva, A.Yu. In the scientific works of Agafonov, MM Bakhtin, AN Leont'ev, creativity is analyzed as a quality of the individual, and the issues of diagnosing creativity are analyzed. In particular, the development of methods for diagnosing creativity is one of the major challenges in the field of science. By the XXI century, this term began to be used in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Especially in Innovative pedagogy, which has begun to take shape as a separate and young branch of pedagogy, we are faced with this term. The purpose of many pedagogical works, such as JG Yuldashev, RAMavlanova, is to study the concept of creativity from a scientific and pedagogical point of view.

Primary school teachers are native teachers;

- keeps abreast of news in their field in an integral and continuous round uses them in his pedagogical activity;
- be able to overcome existing psychological barriers;
- If the creative activity of teachers is taken into account by the management, etc.

Particular attention was paid to the fact that one of the important factors influencing the ways and means of developing the creative abilities of primary school students is teacher-student cooperation. It is known that the educational process has a two-pronged nature and consists of an equal relationship between teacher and students. The teacher who leads this process is the person responsible for the proper organization of the educational process, the proper implementation of the learning objectives and the learning outcomes. However, this does not give rise to the misconception that the educational process is a process that takes place under the full control of the teacher. The demand of the present time is to achieve a positive result not through subjugation, but through a cooperative approach. It should be borne in mind that the formation of students' activities in the educational process is not only a mechanism for mastering the basics of science, but also focuses on the formation of the general socio-cultural abilities of the individual. In our view, the learning situation is a variable system that organizes the learning process and consists of two parts:

- student-teacher collaboration;
- the interaction of the birds with each other.

1. The principle of consistency of content in education. According to him, when a person organizes his activity on the basis of a specific purpose, the continuous formation of this activity is observed.

2. The principle of teacher-student cooperation in connection with independent creative activity.

The following factors hinder the development of creativity in an individual:

Avoiding self-risk;

Thinking and allowing rudeness in behavior;

Personal fantasy and underestimation of imagination;

Being submissive to others;

In any case, just think of winning.

David Lewis's creativity in children

development guidelines

1. With patience to children's questions answer correctly. -

2. Take their questions and opinions seriously.

3. Allocate a separate room or corner for children to do their work.

4. If it is related to the creative process, then do not blame the child for the clutter in the room.

5. Occasionally tell children that you love them and show that they accept them as they are.

Transforming students into learners and learners is not only a prerequisite for the success of the teaching and learning process, but also an important condition for educating them to be well-rounded people.

The student becomes a person of knowledge and education in the process of teaching and educating. Sh.A. Amonashvili emphasizes the need to establish a cooperative relationship with the student in the educational process, saying: The behavior in the learning process is regulated by nature. In an environment where there is kindness, trust, cooperation, respect, the student easily masters the learning tasks. Seeing that his achievements, independent thinking, creative research are highly valued, the student begins to strive for more complex learning tasks.

Students do not become creative on their own. His creative ability is formed through consistent learning, self-study over a period of time, and gradually improves and develops.

Teachers can help students become more creative by working with students and taking into account each of their ideas and making them aware of them. By giving students problem-solving situations and situations, the student's creative approach to finding a solution to the problem helps to develop the emotional-volitional qualities in it. This will give students the opportunity to work on themselves, to study independently, and to increase their inner need.

The concept of 'creativity' is related to the concept of 'creativity'. However, the concept of 'creativity' has not found a proper differentiation in relevant dictionaries

and is not sufficiently defined in creative psychology. Despite the fact that dozens of scientific works have different approaches to this or that aspect of creativity and cover it at different levels, so far there is no single point of view on either the problem itself or the practical questions related to it.

Summarizing the above points, we came to the conclusion that creativity and creativity do not mean exactly the same thing. Because when we say creativity, everyone can think of an invention, a drawing, and so on. But in our research, we took creativity as the ability to find a unique way to the task given in the course of the lesson and to scientifically substantiate it, to think in a new way, to be able to apply it. That is, in our research we will consider the creativity in the field of education, that is, the methodology of developing the creative abilities of primary school students. We came to the conclusion that creativity is a broader concept than creativity.

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